

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY FOR FORECASTING THE VOLUME OF HEAT CONSUMPTION OF URBAN BUILDINGS FOR ENERGY-EFFICIENT MANAGEMENT APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

An informational technology has been developed, which includes an improved calculation model for determining the energy characteristics of buildings. It is distinguished by a combination of modern computer methods of building energy modeling as a complex system, system analysis, history of changes, and grouping of a set of internal and external influencing factors, allowing for forecasting and regulating heating considering the inertia of buildings to changes in weather conditions and operating conditions. Mathematical models and methods for assessing the energy efficiency of buildings have been developed to determine energy efficiency indicators by refining the division of thermal inertia characteristics of building enclosures and changes in weather conditions, thereby reducing discrepancies in determining energy consumption in countries with sharply continental climates. Conditions for the application and comparison of stationary, quasi-stationary, and dynamic methods for determining the energy characteristics of buildings for different time calculations have been determined. Methodological foundations and mathematical models have been developed for forecasting and regulating the heating level based on system analysis and taking into account the history of the influence of four groups of internal and external influencing factors.

Keywords: information technology, heat consumption, regulation, modeling, predicting, energy efficiency

Introduction

Approximately 40% of global energy consumption is attributed to buildings. Therefore, Ukrainian standards are increasingly demanding efficient energy use in buildings. The adequacy of assessing the level of energy efficiency of buildings depends on the use of mathematical models of the energy state of the building as a complex energy system. Therefore, addressing this issue requires the use of mathematical models of varying complexity depending on the tasks being solved.

In accordance with international norms and standards actively implemented in Ukraine, buildings are considered complex energy systems in conjunction with enclosing structures, sources, internal, and external environments. The complex of thermal energy efficiency indicators of a building includes energy assessment and energy consumption. Based on energy consumption values, the energy assessment of the building is determined. The assessment of efficient energy use for heating and cooling is based on the building's energy needs, which are calculated and cannot be easily measured. The development of mathematical models of buildings is an important step in determining building energy efficiency and assessing energy-saving potential.

Despite scientific experience and achievements in this direction, the adaptation and application of modern approaches from global practice to Ukrainian conditions remain unresolved. This underscores the relevance of the research. Thus, the scientific task of the work is to develop and improve methods for determining the energy characteristics of buildings.

Adequate assessment of the level of energy efficiency of buildings depends on the use of mathematical models of the energy state of buildings as complex energy systems. Initially, it is necessary to analyze the level of energy efficiency of the complex of public buildings and determine the main directions for implementing energy-saving measures. The use of mathematical modeling in determining and improving the energy efficiency of buildings is the main assessment tool, so the selection and development of models for modeling the thermal state of buildings is a primary task.

According to statistics on energy consumption in Ukraine, it can be divided into three major groups: industry (up to 28%), transportation (up to 32%), and the residential sector (over 40%) [8]. The peculiarities of Ukraine's economy lie in the fact that in the structure of primary energy resource consumption in Ukraine, gas accounts for about 41% (oil 18.4%, coal 24.3%, nuclear energy and others 16.3%), which is three times more than the world average and twice as much as in Europe. Moreover, the situation is complicated by the fact that despite the general stereotype, the main gas consumers in Ukraine, and moreover, extremely inefficient ones, are not industrial enterprises, but rather the population, communal services, and combined heat and power plants (CHP), which produce thermal and electric energy.

Methodology

Various methods and approaches are used for the research and development of an information technology for predicting the volume of heat consumption in

urban buildings, including: statistical forecasting methods (based on the analysis of historical data on heat consumption and include time series analysis methods, smoothing methods [6]); machine learning methods (utilize algorithms to discover patterns in large datasets; may include neural networks, decision trees, random forests, clustering methods); hybrid methods (combination of statistical methods and machine learning methods to improve forecasting accuracy); artificial intelligence and data analysis (deep learning methods for analyzing and predicting heat consumption volume [11]); big data processing (use of technologies for collecting, storing, and analyzing large datasets to make accurate forecasts); optimization methods (utilization of mathematical models [2–3] and algorithms for optimizing heating systems and reducing energy costs); integration of additional data sources (inclusion of additional data such as meteorological data, building characteristics, energy efficiency data to enhance forecasting).

In this work, the following methods were applied for the research and development of the information technology: methods of analysis and synthesis, mathematical statistics methods, methods of mathematical and simulation modeling, fundamental principles of heat and mass transfer theory, experimental methods for determining the temperature state of premises, a systemic approach considering temperature-weather and operational factors.

Main Part

Ukraine continues to face challenges of inefficient consumption of fuel and energy resources by the population and inadequate technical condition of the vast

majority of existing buildings and energy systems. The low level of energy efficiency of buildings is largely associated with the low thermal resistance of enclosing structures.

Reducing energy consumption for heating buildings can be achieved through various means. In Ukraine, one of the ways is the use of modern thermal insulation materials and technologies at both the design and operational stages (see Figure 1).

The second direction involves the use of renewable and alternative energy sources in distributed generation systems. The third direction is the implementation of automatic control in building heating systems (local heat consumption control). The fourth is the influence on the social factor, operational conditions, and user behavior management.

The average thermal energy savings from implementing energy-efficient measures under the program applied by homeowners' associations and housing cooperatives were as follows: 24% when thermomodernizing walls; 14% when installing energy-efficient transparent structures in common areas. Additionally, significant electricity savings were recorded for lighting common areas (71%) [3].

The level of energy consumption in buildings in Ukraine is decreasing through various avenues and depends on several factors, such as thermal protection of enclosing structures, control of heating engineering systems, climatic conditions, and more. Therefore, to ensure rational use of energy resources for heating, an effective approach to studying the impact of these factors and establishing the potential for energy resource savings is necessary.

Figure 1 – Main directions of reducing energy consumption for heating buildings

Energy efficiency is a metric characterized by the ratio of energy resource utilization efficiency to their consumption. Increasing the level of energy efficiency by a complex or system involves the development of organizational, techno-economic, environmental, technical, and technological aspects of energy production, distribution, transportation, and consumption. Energy consumption is the most influential direction for implementing a complex of energy-saving measures. The

economic system of a region or a specific territorial complex includes the energy system of the region, which consists of: the power supply system, heating system, gas supply system, water supply, and drainage system, among others. A complex of buildings (e.g., a district), according to the methodology of comprehensive analysis, can be considered as a system (S), a set of techniques, processes, and resources necessary for its functioning. By definition, a system is considered as

a set of aggregated components fundamentally necessary for the existence and functioning of the system under study [7]:

$$S = \{Z, STR, TECH, COND\}, \quad (1)$$

Where Z - the set of goals; STR - the set of structures implementing the goals (e.g., production, organizational, etc.); $TECH$ - the set of techniques, technologies, etc., through which the system is implemented; $COND$ - the operating conditions of the system, i.e., considering factors (external, internal) that affect its functioning.

Addressing the challenges of building energy efficiency with consideration of a complex of indicators, namely thermal and thermal inertia characteristics of enclosures, microclimate conditions, operational schedules, climatic conditions, heating and heat dissipation systems, etc., which affect specific energy characteristics (energy efficiency indicators) of a building, requires a systemic approach and is a complex task. Solving these tasks requires the creation of mathematical models for investigating the energy characteristics of buildings. Mathematical models can have different levels of discretization in calculations depending on the tasks at hand, which can simplify or complicate the model.

The information technology for forecasting the volume of heat consumption in urban buildings is designed for use by homeowners' associations and city executive bodies for heat energy accounting.

The heat source is a heat center and electric boilers, which heat an accumulator tank in the basement of the building. In the building, there is a Central Heating Point (CHP).

There is a need for the modernization of CHPs and the implementation of modern individual Heating Points (IHPs) located directly in the heating building for effective heat supply regulation.

During nighttime, when the tariff for consumed electricity is lower, it is necessary to save energy. Depending on the forecast, it is necessary to increase or decrease electricity consumption and regulate boilers accordingly.

The task of the heating system management of the building is to determine the time of heating the heat carrier in the accumulator tank, the expediency of heating the accumulator tank with limited capacity of the electric heater, and regulating the temperature of the heat carrier according to the forecasted outside air temperature.

The task of the heat consumption accounting system includes monitoring the heat consumption in Gigacalories, recalculating electrical energy, and charging the heat accumulator. Sometimes it is advantageous to charge, while other times it is more expensive.

Building heat losses are analyzed over a week or a month.

The task of the building heating control system is to determine the heating time of the heat carrier in the thermal storage tank, the feasibility of heating the thermal accumulator with limited electric heater power, and adjusting the temperature of the heat carrier according to the forecasted outside air temperature [1].

Various software products discussed allow for solving a wide range of tasks. For determining the energy characteristics of buildings, the most common approach is to use existing software products such as EnergyPlus, eQUEST, TRNSYS, ANSYS/FLUENT, SolidWorks, Modelica, etc [10].

Most of Ukraine's buildings were constructed before the 2000s during a period of mass construction. For these buildings, specific characteristics of heating and ventilation are established depending on their purpose, year of construction, and volume [4]. Calculations in Ukraine are conducted based on aggregated heating characteristics according to the KTM2004 standard [12]. There are also cross-industry standards for public buildings on heating requirements, allowing for determining energy consumption depending on the purpose and location of the facility [5]:

$$Q_o^{rik} = Q_o^{\max} \frac{\theta_{int} - \theta_{sr.o}}{\theta_{int} - \theta_{r.o}} n_o \cdot 24, \quad (2)$$

where Q_o^{rik} - the annual heat consumption, kW hours/year; Q_o^{\max} - the maximum heat consumption, kW; Q_{int} - the calculated indoor air temperature during the heating period, °C; $\theta_{sr.o}$ - the average outdoor air temperature during the heating period, °C; $\theta_{r.o}$ - the calculated outdoor air temperature for design, °C; n_o - the duration of the heating period, days; 24 - the operating time of the heating system throughout the day, hours:

$$Q_o^{\max} = \alpha q_o V_z (\theta_{int} - \theta_{r.o}) \cdot 10^{-3}, \quad (3)$$

where α - the coefficient that accounts for the difference between real conditions and calculated conditions; q_o - the specific heating characteristic of the building at the calculated outdoor air temperature $\theta_{r.o} = -30$ °C, (W m³)/K, V_z - the external volume of the building, m³.

The annual energy consumption of the building for heating is determined by the formula:

$$Q_o^{rik} = \sum_{i=1}^n Q_{H.nd.i}, \quad (4)$$

where i - the ordinal number of the heating month; n - the number of heating months; $Q_{H.nd.}$ - the monthly energy consumption for constant heating, kW/h.

$$Q_{H.nd.} = Q_{H.tr} - \eta_{H.gn} Q_{H.gn}, \quad (5)$$

where $Q_{H.tr}$ - monthly total heat transfer by transmission and ventilation, kW/h; $Q_{H.gn}$ - monthly total heat gains in heating mode, kW/h; $\eta_{H.gn}$ - dimensionless monthly utilization coefficient of gains.

$$Q_{H.hr.} = Q_{tr} + Q_{ve}, \quad (6)$$

where Q_{tr} - heat transfer by transmission per month, kW/h; Q_{ve} - ventilation heat transfer, kW/h.

$$Q_{H.gn.} = Q_{int} + Q_{sol}, \quad (7)$$

where Q_{int} – sum of internal heat gains during the given period, kW/h; Q_{sol} – sum of solar heat gains during the given period, kW/h.

$$Q_{tr.} = H_{hr} (\theta_{int} - \theta_e) t, \quad (8)$$

where H_{hr} – overall transmission heat transfer coefficient of the zone, kW/K; θ_{int} – specified temperature of the building zone for heating, °C; θ_e – average monthly outdoor temperature, °C; t – duration of the month for which the calculation is made, hours.

$$Q_{ve} = H_{ve} (\theta_{int} - \theta_e) t, \quad (9)$$

where H_{ve} – overall ventilation heat transfer coefficient, W/K.

The inertial characteristics of the enclosure are taken into account through coefficients for four types of massiveness [9]. For the massiveness of buildings in Ukraine, the standard [12] proposes to use a constant value of the coefficient ($C=80$ W/h/(m²/K)), which somewhat mitigates the inertial characteristics of different buildings.

The model is implemented in the Microsoft Excel software environment. When calculating the energy characteristics of buildings using common stationary and quasi-stationary methods in Ukraine, climatic characteristics for the corresponding region/regional center are used. Specifically, average monthly external temperature indicators, solar heat gains on horizontal and vertical surfaces for the quasi-stationary method, and averages for the heating period are used for the degree-day method. The influence of wind speed and direction in the models of this discretization step is accounted for in an aggregate manner through the normative value of air exchange multiplicity.

Monitoring of building thermal comfort involves activities such as collecting data from heat energy meters, climatic conditions of the surrounding environment, and room temperature, analyzing data, and making decisions regarding the need for thermal comfort

regulation. Ultimately, reports are submitted to higher management levels, and if necessary, recommendations for increasing the efficiency of thermal energy utilization in the facility are provided. The main principles of monitoring include targeted orientation, process continuity, and data objectivity, as well as information structuring, availability of processing tools and algorithms, and controllability of monitoring objects.

Data analysis includes: verification of the consistency of data obtained from heat energy suppliers, calculation of thermal energy savings, comparison of current month's heat consumption with that of a similar period in the previous year, and identification of deviations in heat consumption and determination of their causes.

After studying the system, it was determined that the main functions of the thermal comfort monitoring system are: calculating forecasted thermal comfort indicators for the next day, generating a report on heat supply indicators for the past day, generating a protocol report for the past day, and providing regulatory recommendations for the next 2–3 days.

The system model is built using the ERWin CASE tool. Figure 2 shows the contextual diagram of the building thermal consumption monitoring process.

Figure 3 shows the scheme of business processes implemented within the information technology for predicting the volume of heating consumption in urban buildings.

The input information for the information system consists of monitoring data (room temperature, metering device data), the temperature schedule of the heat supply station (temperature schedules of the heat carrier), and parameters of the climatic conditions of the surrounding environment (daily air temperature).

During the operation of the information system, the following tasks are addressed:

- assessment of the current state of heating supply in the building (data collection, monitoring of building thermal supply);
- analysis of the obtained data (verification of data consistency, comparison of current heat consumption with past periods, identification of deviations);
- forecasting the building's heat energy needs.

Figure 2 – Context diagram of the building heat consumption monitoring system

Figure 3

Business processes of the subject area of forecasting the volume of heat consumption of urban buildings

The output of the information system includes forecasted values of building heating consumption for the next period (day, week, month) and reports (reports on heating supply indicators for a certain period). An automated workstation for remote dispatcher access to the heating system has been implemented, with the ability to export forecast data for energy management applications.

Conclusions

The developed information technology for predicting the volume of heating consumption in urban buildings for energy-efficient management applications, unlike existing ones, contains improved computational models for determining the energy characteristics of buildings. These models combine modern computer methods of building energy modeling as complex systems, historical data on the variation and grouping of the combination of internal and external influencing factors. This allows for forecasting and regulating heating with consideration for the inertia of buildings to changes in weather conditions and operating conditions.

The information technology enables more precise determination of energy efficiency indicators, taking into account the thermal inertia characteristics of building enclosures and changes in weather conditions. This helps reduce discrepancies in determining energy consumption in conditions of a sharply continental climate. Methodological principles and mathematical models have been developed for forecasting and regulating heating levels based on considering the prehistory of the influence of internal and external factors.

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